

SPACE ASTROMETRY

Determination of an inertial frame from observations of minor planets

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Observation of minor planets constitutes one of several possibilities for establishing an inertial reference frame for the proper motions of stars (cf. Høg's note 1). The present note aims at a numerical evaluation of the potentialities of the method.

The present accuracy of astronomical inertial systems is approximately set by the accuracy of the general precession, $0''.15 \text{ cy}^{-1}$ m.e. (Fricke, A & A 54, 363, 1977). Since this is about the mean error that we hope to achieve for the proper motion of a single star, it is desirable that the rotation of the system is known at least one order of magnitude better than this in order to make good use of the several thousand proper motions obtained with the satellite.

It will be shown that observations of minor planets cannot substantially improve our knowledge of absolute proper motions unless they cover a period of at least 5 years. Then we have still made some very optimistic assumptions regarding the accuracy of individual observations and absence of systematic effects.

Assumptions and description of procedure

Scanning mode Only Option A is considered. Revolving scanning, $\zeta = 40^\circ$ and $K = 6.75$. Field of view $0^\circ.9$ normal to the scanning direction.

Mean error per orbit $\sigma = 0''.0018 \text{ dex}[0.2(B - 9)]$, where B is the blue magnitude of the planet at the time of observation. With 8^s observing time per orbit this corresponds to $\sigma_{1s} = 0''.005$ for a $B = 9$ star, which is about the mean error from photon statistics only for a 32×8 cm aperture.

Objects Observations of planets are possible only near quadrature. Table 1 lists the five brightest minor planets at mean quadrature and some of their characteristics. There are about 50 minor planets with $B \leq 13$ at mean quadrature, but the five brightest contribute more than

60 % of their combined intensity. Thus we should not expect that an observing program with 50 planets gives a much better result than one with only the five planets considered here.

On the other hand, there are some problems with the bright asteroids too. Their finite apparent diameters deteriorate the observations in different ways:

1. There are systematic displacements (D_1) due to the phases which will influence the determination of the mean motions and ω_z .
2. There are random (?) displacements (D_2) due to non-sphericity and surface markings, adding to the mean error per observation.
3. The intensity modulation behind the grid is reduced by a factor k , with a corresponding reduction of the timing accuracy.

Estimates of D_1 , D_2 and k are given in Table 1. Effects 2 and 3 are not included in the assumed σ .

Distribution of observations It is assumed that the five planets are observed at every opportunity during 2.5, 3.5 or 5 years, each period centred on 1970.0. The resulting number of epochs and observations are given in Table 2. 'One observation' = one orbit during which the planet is observed in both fields of view; 'one epoch' = a group of consecutive orbits during which the planet is observed.

Fig. 1 shows the positions of the Earth and Eunomia at the times of observation (34 epochs).

Observation equations There are 39 unknowns: six corrections to orbital elements of the Earth and planets, and three components ω_x , ω_y , ω_z of the rotation of the provisional reference system in an inertial frame. (xyz are standard ecliptical coordinates, x towards $\lambda = 0^\circ$, z towards $\beta = 90^\circ$.)

For planet no. i ($i = 0$ for the Earth) the unknowns are:

Δl_i = correction to the mean orbital longitude,

Δp_i , Δq_i , Δr_i = rotational corrections to the orbital plane around three axes pointing towards perihelion, 90° in advance in the orbit, and normal to the orbital plane,

Δn_i = correction to the mean motion, and

Δe_i = correction to the eccentricity.

The unknown Δn is preferred to Δa , the correction to the mean distance from the Sun, for the following reason. The distance scale is fixed by putting $a_0 = 1$ and the unit of time is defined by an atomic clock. Thus the mean motion of the Earth (the length of the sidereal year) must be derived from observation and similarly the mean motions of the other planets, while their mean distances follow from Kepler's third law. The same set of unknowns can then be used for the Earth and the other planets.

The observation equations are formed as follows.

1. Corrections $\Delta \vec{r}_i$ to the heliocentric rectangular coordinates of the planets and the Earth are expressed in terms of the unknowns (Clemence, Methods of Celestial Mechanics, Ch. 9, Set III).
2. The geocentric corrections $\Delta \vec{\rho}_i = \Delta \vec{r}_i - \Delta \vec{r}_0$ and the rotation vector $\vec{\omega}$ then gives the corrections in longitude and latitude at time t

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \lambda \cos \beta \\ \Delta \beta \end{bmatrix} = \rho^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \lambda & \cos \lambda & 0 \\ -\sin \beta \cos \lambda & -\sin \beta \sin \lambda & \cos \beta \end{bmatrix} (\Delta \vec{\rho} + t \vec{\omega} \times \vec{\rho}),$$

where $\vec{\rho}$ is the geocentric vector to the planet.

3. Finally, the correction along the scanning direction is $\Delta \lambda \cos \beta \sin \theta + \Delta \beta \cos \theta = (O - C)$, $\theta =$ position angle of scan.

The normal equations and the covariance matrix are computed as usual, yielding the mean errors of the unknowns and the correlations between them.

Results

A selection of results are given in Tables 3, 4 and 5.

It is, however, unrealistic to assume that we have no prior knowledge of the motions of the planets. In particular, it appears that Δr , Δn and Δe can in principle be determined with superior accuracy from radar observations, while the other three unknowns are intimately connected with the provisional coordinate system employed and therefore cannot be determined without making reference to the stars. Hence I give in Table 3 also the mean errors of $\vec{\omega}$ for 3.5 years observation under the hypothesis that Δr , Δn and Δe are perfectly known for all planets, the Earth included. However except for ω_2 the improvement is

not very great and the desired improvement by one order of magnitude over the present accuracy is still out of reach.

Table 1. The brightest minor planets at mean quadrature.

a = mean distance from the Sun

e = eccentricity

i = inclination

B = blue magnitude at mean quadrature

R = apparent semi-diameter at m. q.

D_1 = displacement of centre of light due to phases

D_2 = amplitude of displacement of centre of light due to non-sphericity and surface markings (D_1 and D_2 from Lindegren, A & A 57, 55, 1977)

k = factor by which the light intensity modulation behind the grid is decreased, $k = 3(\sin f - f \cos f)/f^3$, $f = 2\pi R/s$, s = grid period.

Name	a	e	i	B	R	D_1	D_2	$k_{s=1''5/''75}$
4 Vesta	2.36	0.088	7 ^o .1	8.4	0".16	0".025	0".004	.96/.83
1 Ceres	2.77	0.079	10.6	8.9	0.27	0.037	0.003	.88 .57
2 Pallas	2.77	0.235	34.8	9.9	0.15	0.020	0.005	.96 .85
15 Eunomia	2.64	0.185	11.7	10.8	0.07	0.010	0.008	.99 .97
6 Hebe	2.43	0.203	14.8	10.9	0.06	0.009	0.002	.99 .97

Table 2. Number of observations and epochs for the various planets and mission lengths.

Planet	No. of observations			No. of epochs		
	2.5	3.5	5 yr	2.5	3.5	5 yr
Vesta	89	112	132	17	23	29
Ceres	70	80	150	16	19	32
Pallas	140	186	267	18	28	42
Eunomia	95	130	164	17	26	34
Hebe	135	160	232	18	25	35
Average	106	134	189	17	24	34

Table 3. Mean errors of ω_x , ω_y , ω_z for different mission lengths. Three minor planets (Vesta, Ceres, Pallas) or five (+Eunomia, Hebe) are observed. Values in parentheses are the mean errors if Δr , Δn and Δe are exactly known for all planets, including the Earth. Unit: arcsec/cy.

	2.5	3.5	5 yr	2.5	3.5	5 yr
ω_x	0.14	0.075 (0.062)	0.034	0.18	0.092	0.038
ω_y	0.15	0.070 (0.056)	0.036	0.18	0.073	0.041
ω_z	0.68	0.21 (0.055)	0.12	1.04	0.25	0.14
	Five planets			Three planets		

Table 4. Mean errors of the elements of the Earth and the five minor planets for 3.5 years of observation.

Element	Unit	Earth	Vesta	Ceres	Pallas	Eunomia	Hebe
Δl	0"001	3.3	1.3	5.1	1.3	2.7	4.2
Δp	0"001	1.5	0.70	0.99	1.4	2.0	1.3
Δq	0"001	1.4	0.92	1.1	1.8	1.6	2.5
Δr	0"001	220	29	41	5.8	33	24
Δn	"/cy	0.36	0.38	1.1	0.26	1.1	0.80
Δe	10^{-9}	20	6.1	29	12	18	15

Table 5. Correlations between the elements of Earth and the rotation components ω_x , ω_y , ω_z (solution with all planets, 3.5 y).

	ω_x	ω_y	ω_z	Δl_o	Δp_o	Δq_o	Δr_o	Δn_o	Δe_o
ω_x	1.00								
ω_y	.34	1.00							
ω_z	.38	.31	1.00						
Δl_o	-.22	-.13	-.05	1.00					
Δp_o	.09	-.12	-.15	-.04	1.00				
Δq_o	.09	-.08	-.03	-.19	.16	1.00			
Δr_o	.07	.13	-.08	-.16	-.25	-.28	1.00		
Δn_o	.09	.08	.35	.07	-.13	-.06	.11	1.00	
Δe_o	.44	.10	.52	-.03	-.18	.00	.29	.26	1.00

Fig. 1. The relative positions of the Earth and Eunomia at the 34 epochs of observation in an interval of 5 years.

